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Factors Influencing the Online Shopping Behaviour among Different Category of Shoppers

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Abstract

Modern day customers prefer online shopping not only for high level of convenience, but also because of the broader selection; competitive pricing and greater access to information. This study aims to drawing association between the category of online buyers (Simplifiers, Surfers, Connectors, Bargain Shoppers, Routine Followers and Sportsters) and factors that influences the IT professional to choice the online shopping. The current study is both explorative and descriptive in nature. The study is focused on the IT professionals working Coimbatore city. It was observed that there are 83 IT companies are functioning in Coimbatore city. In the second stage of the study, thirty per cent of the IT companies were chosen as samples for the effective conduct of this study. From each company a small sample of thirty respondents were chosen, that was summed to 750 respondents in total. The studies found that majority of the respondents' were highly influenced by various factors like: browsing and searching for products, ease and convenience, obtaining information from the firms and comparing product features to shop in online. Followed by the sample respondents have opined that they were convinced by the online shopping features like: convenience of sales person contact, exchange facilities, more offers / discounts and convenient mode of product delivery. The study concluded by stating that there exists association between the category of customers (simplifiers, connectors, sportsters, routine followers and surfer) and the factors that influenced them to shop online .However, it is has been observed that bargain buyers always seek for best online deals, offers, coupons while they buy a product, so there always look and compare the product available on virtual and in brick retailers stores, thus, there exists no association between the bargain shoppers category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.

Keywords: Online Shoppers, Category of Online Shoppers, Factors influencing Online Shopping.

Introduction

The changing consumer behaviour over the decade has forced the retailer to understand the psychology of the virtual consumers¹. Though online shopping is very common outside India, its growth in Indian Market is in nascent stage. Modern day customers prefer online shopping not only for high level of convenience, but also because of the broader selection; competitive pricing and greater access to information. From the organizations point

of view online shopping increases their customer value and the building of sustainable capabilities and also support them in increasing their profits. Many of the modern day consumers also feel that online stores are usually available 24 hours a day, and many consumers have Internet access both at work and at home. Not all online shoppers liking are alike. Different people have different expectations and goals when it comes to shopping i.e., their shopping motives varies from one to another. In

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Factors Influencing the Online Shopping Behaviour among Different Category of Shoppers

Table: 1
Types of Online Shoppers

Type of Shoppers	Qualities	Discussion
The simplifiers	Quick Shoppers	Impatient shoppers spending a few hours' per month online. Create positive emotions through your design to help with impatience
The surfers	Research-Led Shoppers	On average these category of customers spent 32 per cent online. Allow browsers to buy products quickly. Create simple steps to do so (e.g. browse, checkout and delivery).
The connectors	Traditional Shoppers	Prefer brick stores. Offer online exclusives but set a limit on online exclusive stock.
Bargain shoppers	Price-Driven Shoppers	Happiest once deals are found. Offer free delivery from time to time. Think about seasonal offers.
The routine Followers	Addicted Shoppers	Frequent web users who read a range of information. Write descriptively. Think about using lists, photos and descriptions.
The sportsters	Entertainment Shoppers	Enjoy sport websites. Cater for everyone. Visual people like photos. Audio-based users prefer sound clips and video files, for example

Source: <https://geraldmurphysearch.wordpress.com/2013/10/07/types-of-online-shoppers/>

short, their post-purchase behaviour is critical in the marketing perspective, as it eventually affects consumers' perception of satisfaction/dissatisfaction with the product/service.

Generally, it has been observed that various category of online shoppers focuses on the issues like value of the product, the shopping experience, the quality of service offered by the website like product delivery, payments etc., and the risk perceptions of Internet retail shopping.

Statement of Problem

In India online shopping is considered it is more popular among the youth and working professionals in India. Increased Internet penetration, improved security measures, convenience of shopping in lives pressed for time, and, of course, dozens of retailers to choose from these are a few factors that are attracting more and more consumers to shop online. There are various factors which have been instrumental in bringing about this change with the major ones being the increase in mass media exposure and also the rising number of

social networking apps targeting the youth and professionals. Moreover, with the increasing internet literacy, the prospect of online marketing is increasing in India. The consumers indulging in online shopping consider many factors some factors have been identified by earlier researcher and there are many factors that influences online buying practices have to still explore. This study aims to analyse and identify the factors that influence the online shopping among differed category online behaviour shoppers.

Objectives

This study aims to drawing association between the category of online buyers (Simplifiers, Surfers, Connectors, Bargain Shoppers, Routine Followers and Sportsters) and factors that influences the IT professional to choice the online shopping.

Hypothesis of the study

There exists association between the various category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.

Research Design

The current study is both explorative and descriptive in nature. The study is focused on the IT professionals working Coimbatore city. Population of the study comprised of private IT companies functioning in Coimbatore. The current research work is based on the multi-stage random sampling technique. In the first stage of sampling, it was observed that there are 83 IT companies are functioning in Coimbatore city. In the second stage of the study, thirty per cent of the IT companies were chosen as samples for the effective conduct of this study. From each company a small sample of thirty respondents were chosen, that was summed to 750 respondents in total.

Results and Discussion

The study observed that 36.93 per cent of IT professionals who shop online are designated as entry level executive and 41.47 per cent of IT professional earn less than Rs.15, 000 per month. The descriptive study conducted among 750 respondents, constitute 63.47 per cent of male respondents are male and 36.53 per cent of female samples subjects. The study observed that 54.27 per cent of the rural online shoppers are under the age of 25 years, 43.20 per cent of them are in the age group of 25-40 years. Out of the 750 respondents taken for the study, it is observed that 61.33 per cent of the online shoppers are postgraduates, 32.40 per cent of them come under the under graduates, 6.27 per cent has completed professionals degree. Their socio-economic status revealed that 54 per cent of IT professionals are married, of which 73.73 per cent belong to the joint family set-ups.

Most of the consumers' have exhibited high degree of awareness towards the Shopping Websites like: Amazon, **Flipkart.com, Tradus, Snapdeal.com, Yebhi and Maaptol web sites. It was observed that** 50.67 per cent of the online shoppers said that they shopped during

occasionally and 30.53 per cent of the respondents used to purchase for monthly. Further, it was found that 48.27 per cent online shoppers involved shopping for the past one to three years, 43.60 per cent of online shoppers operated by self-motivating and 56.27 per cent of customers' using online shopping through mobile phone internet. The shopping pattern of IT professional was found to be more in Mobiles Phone (95.33 per cent), Books (91.47 per cent), shoes and sporting goods (82.80 per cent), home furnishing (82.40 per cent), laptops (82.13 per cent), Food & Groceries (78.67 per cent), Electronics Goods (78.27 per cent), Watches (76.93 per cent), Home Appliances (76.53 per cent), Mobiles Phones Accessories (75.60 per cent), toys & Baby items (70.67 per cent), Jewellery & Ornaments (62.67 per cent) and Fashion Apparel (62.67 per cent). It was further inferred that 95.20 per cent of the sample respondents have said that they book railway ticket on online, 91.33 per cent of respondents pay E-Governance bills, 86.67 per cent of respondents make payments to retailer.

In Exhibit 1, the current study majority of the respondents were sportsters (18.67 per cent). Followed by it was observed that routine followers (17.60 per cent), simplifiers (16.27 per cent), connectors (16.13 per cent), surfer (15.73 per cent) and bargain shoppers (15.60).

SEM was performed to with objectives of drawing association between the category of online buyers (Simplifiers, Surfers, Connectors, Bargain Shoppers, Routine Followers and Sportsters) and factors that influences the IT professional to choice the online shopping.

In the Table 4, on the basis of these measurements, the result of the study shows that the proposed model has a reasonable data fit $\chi^2=3450.744$ ($p=.000$), GFI=.638, AGFI=.061, TLI=-.068, CFI=.539, NFI=.540, PNFI=.233, PCFI=.233, RFI=-.067, IFI=.545, RMSEA=.000).

Factors Influencing the Online Shopping Behaviour among Different Category of Shoppers

Exhibit 1: Classification of Online Shoppers

Table 2: Variables Expansion

SIMPFIR	Simplifiers	MOROFD	More Offer / Discounts
SURFERS	Surfers	LAPRCA	Large Product Categories
CONNECTOR	Connectors	WESTRSD	Well- Structured Retail Store Design
BARSHOPP	Bargain Shoppers	HISETR	High Security & Trust
ROUTFOL	Routine Followers	CONMOPD	Convenient Mode of product Delivery
SPORTSTER	Sportsters	POBRAVA	Popular Brand Availability
TIMCON	Time Convenience	EXCHFAC	Exchange Facility
MOPROV	More Product Variety	CONSPC	Convenience of sales person contact
ECOPRI	Economic Prices	OTHERS	Others

Table 3: Testing of Hypotheses Results Factors that Influences the it Professional for Opting Online Shopping

Ho	Hypotheses	Hypothetical Relationship	Results
H1	There exists association between the simplifiers category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.	Positive	Confirmed
H2	There exists association between the surfers category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.	Positive	Confirmed
H3	There exists association between the connectors category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.	Positive	Confirmed
H4	There exists association between the bargain shoppers category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.	Negative	Not Confirmed
H5	There exists association between the routine follwers category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.	Positive	Confirmed
H6	There exists association between the sportsters category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.	Positive	Confirmed

Exhibit 3: Structural Equation Modelling Analysis Goodness-Fit Model

Table 4: Chi-Square Result and Goodness of Fit Indices of the Proposed Model

Fit Indices	Obtained Value	Accepted Thresholds Levels	Acceptable Value
χ^2	3450.744	NA	NA
Scaled χ^2/df	55	<0.05	<0.05
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	.638	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	.061	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)	-.068	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	.539	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	.540	Value Greater than 0.95	0-1
Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	.233	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Parsimony Comparative Fit Index (PCFI)	.233	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Relative Fit Index (RFI)	-.067	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	.545	0=Poor Fit, 1=Good Fit	0-1
Root Mean Square Approximation Method (RMSEA)	.000	Value less than 0.07	.05 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

Level of Significance: 5 per cent

Factors Influencing the Online Shopping Behaviour among Different Category of Shoppers

Table 5: Path Analysis Structure Maximum Likelihood –Regression Weightage

Path		Unstandardized Estimates (β)	S.E	C.R	P Value	Relationship
The Simplifiers of Categories						
TIMCON	<---	SIMPFIR	-.181	.037	-4.878	000 Significant
MOPROV	<---	SIMPFIR	.355	.045	7.859	000 Significant
ECOPRI	<---	SIMPFIR	.072	.039	1.834	.067 Insignificant
MOROFD	<---	SIMPFIR	.181	.048	3.770	000 Significant
LAPRCA	<---	SIMPFIR	.295	.049	5.970	000 Significant
WESTRSD	<---	SIMPFIR	.375	.049	7.582	000 Significant
HISETR	<---	SIMPFIR	.369	.039	9.399	000 Significant
COMMOPD	<---	SIMPFIR	.031	.046	.663	.508 Insignificant
POBRAVA	<---	SIMPFIR	.446	.051	8.729	000 Significant
EXCHFAC	<---	SIMPFIR	.217	.049	4.415	000 Significant
CONSPC	<---	SIMPFIR	.127	.051	2.499	.012 Significant
OTHERS	<---	SIMPFIR	.067	.033	2.026	.043 Significant
The Surfers of Categories						
TIMCON	<---	SURFERS	-.059	.028	-2.139	.032 Significant
MOPROV	<---	SURFERS	-.014	.034	-.424	.671 Insignificant
ECOPRI	<---	SURFERS	.072	.029	2.468	.014 Significant
MOROFD	<---	SURFERS	-.299	.036	-8.317	000 Significant
LAPRCA	<---	SURFERS	.327	.037	8.858	000 Significant
WESTRSD	<---	SURFERS	.265	.037	7.166	000 Significant
HISETR	<---	SURFERS	-.081	.029	-2.746	.006 Significant
COMMOPD	<---	SURFERS	-.054	.035	-1.557	.119 Insignificant
POBRAVA	<---	SURFERS	.094	.038	2.466	.014 Significant
EXCHFAC	<---	SURFERS	-.150	.037	-4.079	000 Significant
CONSPC	<---	SURFERS	.218	.038	5.734	000 Significant
OTHERS	<---	SURFERS	-.121	.025	-4.917	000 Significant
The Connectors of Categories						
TIMCON	<---	CONNECTOR	.069	.030	2.331	000 Significant
MOPROV	<---	CONNECTOR	.078	.036	2.146	.032 Significant
ECOPRI	<---	CONNECTOR	.260	.031	8.268	000 Significant
MOROFD	<---	CONNECTOR	.155	.039	4.024	000 Significant
LAPRCA	<---	CONNECTOR	-.053	.040	-1.345	.179 Insignificant
WESTRSD	<---	CONNECTOR	-.122	.040	-3.065	.002 Significant
HISETR	<---	CONNECTOR	.011	.031	.344	.731 Insignificant
COMMOPD	<---	CONNECTOR	.230	.037	6.172	000 Significant
POBRAVA	<---	CONNECTOR	-.347	.041	-8.475	000 Significant
EXCHFAC	<---	CONNECTOR	.035	.039	.890	.374 Insignificant
CONSPC	<---	CONNECTOR	-.042	.041	-1.024	.006 Significant
OTHERS	<---	CONNECTOR	.069	.026	2.628	.009 Insignificant

Level of Significance: 5 Per cent

Table 5 (a): Path Analysis Structure Maximum Likelihood –Regression Weightage

Path			Unstandardized Estimates (β)	S.E	C.R	P Value	Relationship
Bargain Shoppers							
TIMCON	<---	BARSHOPP	-.084	.033	-2.558	.011	Significant
MOPROV	<---	BARSHOPP	-.045	.040	-1.113	.266	Insignificant
ECOPRI	<---	BARSHOPP	-.143	.035	-4.107	000	Significant
MOROFD	<---	BARSHOPP	-.060	.043	-1.394	.163	Insignificant
LAPRCA	<---	BARSHOPP	-.022	.044	-.512	.609	Insignificant
WESTRSD	<---	BARSHOPP	-.055	.044	-1.251	.211	Insignificant
HISETR	<---	BARSHOPP	-.048	.035	-1.381	.167	Insignificant
COMMOPD	<---	BARSHOPP	-.195	.041	-4.731	000	Significant
POBRAVA	<---	BARSHOPP	-.018	.045	-.407	.684	Insignificant
EXCHFAC	<---	BARSHOPP	-.131	.044	-2.999	.003	Significant
CONSPC	<---	BARSHOPP	.095	.045	2.101	.036	Significant
OTHERS	<---	BARSHOPP	-.259	.029	-8.849	000	Significant
TIMCON	<---	ROUTFOL	.138	.037	3.675	000	Significant
The Routine Followers							
MOPROV	<---	ROUTFOL	.469	.046	10.275	000	Significant
ECOPRI	<---	ROUTFOL	.186	.040	4.675	000	Significant
MOROFD	<---	ROUTFOL	.140	.049	2.870	.004	Significant
LAPRCA	<---	ROUTFOL	-.462	.050	-9.234	000	Significant
WESTRSD	<---	ROUTFOL	-.504	.050	-10.079	000	Significant
HISETR	<---	ROUTFOL	-.336	.040	-8.453	000	Significant
COMMOPD	<---	ROUTFOL	-.179	.047	-3.807	000	Significant
POBRAVA	<---	ROUTFOL	-.237	.052	-4.584	000	Significant
EXCHFAC	<---	ROUTFOL	-.317	.050	-6.378	000	Significant
CONSPC	<---	ROUTFOL	.023	.051	.452	.651	Insignificant
OTHERS	<---	ROUTFOL	.056	.033	1.680	.093	Insignificant
The Sportsters of Categories							
TIMCON	<---	SPORTSTER	-.042	.030	-1.389	.165	Insignificant
MOPROV	<---	SPORTSTER	-.042	.037	-1.143	.253	Insignificant
ECOPRI	<---	SPORTSTER	.066	.032	2.069	.039	Significant
MOROFD	<---	SPORTSTER	-.193	.039	-4.946	000	Significant
LAPRCA	<---	SPORTSTER	.299	.040	7.465	000	Significant
WESTRSD	<---	SPORTSTER	.482	.040	12.045	000	Significant
HISETR	<---	SPORTSTER	.156	.032	4.903	000	Significant
COMMOPD	<---	SPORTSTER	.222	.038	5.899	000	Significant
POBRAVA	<---	SPORTSTER	.336	.041	8.123	000	Significant
EXCHFAC	<---	SPORTSTER	.348	.040	8.748	000	Significant
CONSPC	<---	SPORTSTER	.147	.041	3.578	000	Significant
OTHERS	<---	SPORTSTER	-.079	.027	-2.947	.003	Significant

Level of Significance: 5 Per cent

Factors Influencing the Online Shopping Behaviour among Different Category of Shoppers

The measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers (**Simplifiers**): Time Convenience ($\beta = -.181$, $P = .000$), More Product Variety ($\beta = .355$, $P = .000$), More Offer / Discounts ($\beta = .181$, $P = .000$), Large Product Categories ($\beta = .295$, $P = .000$), Well-Structured Retail Store Design ($\beta = .375$, $P = .000$), High Security & Trust ($\beta = .369$, $P = .000$), Popular Brand Availability ($\beta = .446$, $P = .000$), Exchange Facility ($\beta = .217$, $P = .000$), Convenience of sales person contact ($\beta = .127$, $P = .012$) and Others ($\beta = .067$, $P = .043$) were found to significant. And the measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers: Economic Prices ($\beta = .072$, $P = .067$) and Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta = .031$, $P = .508$) were found to insignificant.

It was observed that the measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers (**Surfers**): Time Convenience ($\beta = -.059$, $P = .000$), Economic Prices ($\beta = .072$, $P = .014$), More Offer / Discounts ($\beta = -.299$, $P = .000$), Large Product Categories ($\beta = .327$, $P = .000$), Well-Structured Retail Store Design ($\beta = .265$, $P = .000$), High Security & Trust ($\beta = -.081$, $P = .006$), Popular Brand Availability ($\beta = -.094$, $P = .014$), Exchange Facility ($\beta = -.150$, $P = .000$), Convenience of sales person contact ($\beta = .218$, $P = .000$), and Others ($\beta = -.121$, $P = .000$) were found to significant. The measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers: More Product Variety ($\beta = -.014$, $P = .671$) and Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta = -.054$, $P = .119$) were found to insignificant.

The study found that the co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers (**Connectors**): Time Convenience ($\beta = -.069$, $P = .000$), More Product Variety ($\beta = .078$, $P = .032$), Economic Prices ($\beta = .260$, $P = .000$), More Offer / Discounts ($\beta = .155$, $P = .000$), Well-Structured Retail Store Design ($\beta = -.122$,

$P = .002$), Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta = .230$, $P = .002$) and Popular Brand Availability ($\beta = -.347$, $P = .000$) were found to significant. The measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers: Large Product Categories ($\beta = -.053$, $P = .179$), High Security & Trust ($\beta = .011$, $P = .731$), Exchange Facility ($\beta = -.035$, $P = .374$), Convenience of sales person contact ($\beta = -.042$, $P = .306$), Others ($\beta = .069$, $P = .009$) were found to insignificant.

Further, it has been observed the measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers (**Bargain Shoppers**): Time Convenience ($\beta = -.084$, $P = .011$), Economic Prices ($\beta = -.143$, $P = .000$), Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta = -.195$, $P = .000$), Exchange Facility ($\beta = -.131$, $P = .003$), Convenience of sales person contact ($\beta = .095$, $P = .036$), Others ($\beta = -.259$, $P = .000$) and Time Convenience ($\beta = .138$, $P = .000$) were found to significant. The measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers: More Product Variety ($\beta = -.045$, $P = .266$) More Offer / Discounts ($\beta = -.060$, $P = .163$), Large Product Categories ($\beta = -.022$, $P = .609$), Well-Structured Retail Store Design ($\beta = -.055$, $P = .211$), High Security & Trust ($\beta = -.048$, $P = .167$) and Popular Brand Availability ($\beta = -.018$, $P = .684$) were found to insignificant.

The measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers (**Routine Followers**): More Product Variety ($\beta = .469$, $P = .000$), Economic Prices ($\beta = .186$, $P = .000$), More Offer / Discounts ($\beta = .140$, $P = .004$), Large Product Categories ($\beta = -.462$, $P = .000$), Well-Structured Retail Store Design ($\beta = .504$, $P = .000$), High Security & Trust ($\beta = -.336$, $P = .004$), Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta = -.179$, $P = .000$), Popular Brand Availability ($\beta = -.237$, $P = .000$), Exchange Facility ($\beta = -.317$, $P = .000$) were found to significant. The

measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers: Convenience of sales person contact ($\beta=.023$, $P=.651$), and others ($\beta=.056$, $P=.093$) were found to insignificant.

The measure of co-efficient of variances tested between the categories of online buyers (**Sportsters**): Economic Prices ($\beta=.066$, $P=.039$), More Offer / Discounts ($\beta=-.193$, $P=.000$), Large Product Categories ($\beta=.299$, $P=.000$), Well-Structured Retail Store Design ($\beta=.482$, $P=.000$), High Security & Trust ($\beta=.156$, $P=.000$), Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta=.482$, $P=.000$), High Security & Trust ($\beta=.156$, $P=.000$), Convenient Mode of product Delivery ($\beta=.222$, $P=.000$), Popular Brand Availability ($\beta=.336$, $P=.000$), Exchange Facility ($\beta=.336$, $P=.000$), Exchange Facility ($\beta=.348$, $P=.000$), Convenience of sales person contact ($\beta=.147$, $P=.000$), Others ($\beta=-.079$, $P=.003$) were found to significant. Time Convenience ($\beta=-.042$, $P=.165$) and More Product Variety ($\beta=.042$, $P=.253$), were found to insignificant.

Findings and Conclusion

It has been clearly observed that, majority of the respondents' were highly influenced by various factors like: browsing and searching for products, ease and convenience, obtaining information from the firms and comparing product features to shop in online. Followed by the sample respondents have opined that they were convinced by the online shopping features like: convenience of sales person contact, exchange facilities, more offers / discounts and convenient mode of product delivery. Further it has been inferred that most of the online shoppers were moderately influenced by the features like: time convenience, economic prices, high security and trust and large product categories have attracted most of the online shoppers. It was observed that respondents were least influenced by the

features like: popular brand availability, well-structured retail store design and more product variety have attracted more consumers to shop on online.

The study concluded by stating that there exists association between the category of customers (simplifiers, connectors, sportsters, routine followers and surfer) and the factors that influenced them to shop online. However, it has been observed that bargain buyers always seek for best online deals, offers, coupons while they buy a product, so there always look and compare the product available on virtual and in brick retailers stores, thus, there exists no association between the bargain shoppers category of customers and the factors that influenced them to shop online.

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